

Friedel and Crafts' Reaction with Phenolic Acids.

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Although the occurrence, in nature, of hydroxyanthraquinone carboxylic acids like munjisthin, rhein, pseudopurpurin etc. is by no means rare, very few attempts appear to have been made for the direct synthesis of carboxylated benzoic acids from which such anthraquinone carboxylic acids could be obtained by ring-closure. Limpricht (*Annalen*, 1898, 303, 274) condensed phthalyl chloride with hydroxybenzoic esters and obtained in the case of salicylic ester a benzoylbenzoic acid which he named phthalylsalicylic acid but he did not determine the constitution of the substance.

We have tried to condense phthalic anhydride with diverse phenolic esters in the hope that such a reaction would give substituted benzoylbenzoic acids, from which anthraquinone carboxylic acids could be obtained.

The condensation of salicylic ester with phthalic anhydride in acetylene tetrachloride medium, in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride gave a product melting at 248°, identical with the phthalylsalicylic acid of Limpricht (*loc. cit.*). Now the condensation may have taken place either in *o*- or *p*-position to the hydroxyl group although as Ullmann and Schmidt (*Ber.*, 1919, 52, 2098), have shown in the case of the condensation of phenols and phthalic anhydride in acetylene tetrachloride medium, condensation in *o*-position to the hydroxyl group was more probable.

To settle this question, several experiments were tried with various other hydroxy acids with the following results:

1. From *o*-cresotinic acid (methyl ester), a benzoylbenzoic acid was obtained having properties very similar to that obtained from salicylic ester.

2. *p*-Cresotinic ester, on similar treatment gave no reaction.

3. *p*-Hydroxybenzoic ester gave no reaction.

4. There was also no reaction with *m*-hydroxybenzoic ester.

From the above it may be reasonably concluded that, under the conditions of the experiment, combination takes place only in *p*-position to a hydroxyl group but that no combination takes place in *o*-position to a hydroxyl or a carboxyl group.

Having thus determined the probable position of the link between the two benzene nuclei, we next attempted the closing up of the anthraquinone ring, with (4'-hydroxy-3'-carboxybenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid (I) as also with its methylation product but without success.

The preparation of the anthraquinone *via* anthrone was next thought of and for this purpose the acid (I) as also its methyl ether were subjected to the action of zinc dust and hydrochloric acid in acetic acid solution (Bistrzycki and Krauer, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1923, 6, 753). Several ring-closing experiments were tried with the reduction product but no anthraquinone was formed, the unchanged mother substance being obtained in every case.

On a careful examination of the reduction product it was found that a lactone had resulted by the partial reduction of the -CO- group to a -CHOH- group.

Reduction with zinc and caustic soda (Bistrzycki and Schepper, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2792), and also with zinc dust and ammonia in presence of copper sulphate (Scholl and Neovius, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 1080), yielded the same lactone.

EXPERIMENTAL.

(3'-Carboxy-4'-hydroxybenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid, (I).—Powdered phthalic anhydride (10 g.) was mixed with methyl salicylate (10 g.) in a flask containing 50 c. c. of acetylene tetrachloride and finely powdered aluminium chloride (25 g.) gradually added to the mixture with frequent shaking. The flask was then heated on the water-bath for about 3-4 hours and finally on the oil-bath at 125° for a short time. The contents of the flask were then decomposed by adding ice and distillation in steam whereby acetylene tetrachloride and unchanged salicylic acid were removed. The crude acid thus obtained was dissolved in soda solution, filtered and precipitated with hydrochloric acid and further purified as the calcium salt and reprecipitated with hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from acetic acid in aggregates, m. p. 248°. (Found: C, 63.37; H, 3.44. $C_{15}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 62.94; H, 3.49 per cent.). The substance is identical with the phthalylsalicylic acid of Limpricht (*loc. cit.*).

(3'-Carboxy-4'-methoxybenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid (II).—The acid (I) was methylated with dimethyl sulphate and caustic soda in the usual manner. Aggregates from acetic acid, m. p. 232°. (Found: C, 63.89; H 4.04. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 64.0; H, 4.0 per cent.).

Methyl-(3'-carbomethoxy-4'-hydroxybenzoyl)-2-benzoate (III).—The acid (I) was esterified with methyl alcohol and sulphuric acid in the usual manner. Rectangular plates from aqueous alcohol, m. p. 130-31°. (Found: C, 64.67; H, 4.46. $C_{17}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 64.97; H, 4.46 per cent.).

Methyl-(3'-carbomethoxy-4'-methoxybenzoyl)-2-benzoate (IV).—This was obtained by esterifying (II). Rectangular plates from aqueous alcohol, m. p. 105-06°. (Found: C, 65.83; H, 5.03. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 65.85; H, 4.88 per cent.).

(3'-Carboxy-4'-hydroxyphenyl)-2-phthalide (V).—The acid (I) (5g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (100 c. c.) and treated with extrafine zinc dust and after the gradual addition of hydrochloric acid (d 1.19, 10 c. c.) heated nearly to boiling for 6 hours. The mixture was filtered hot and carefully diluted with hot water. The precipitate was taken up with dilute soda solution, filtered and acidified with hydrochloric acid. It crystallises in plates from aqueous alcohol, m. p. 211-12°, yield about 3.5 g. (Found: C, 66.26; H, 3.89. $C_{15}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 66.66; H, 3.70 per cent.).

(3'-Carboxy-4'-methoxyphenyl)-2-phthalide, (VI).—This was obtained by reducing (III) in the same manner as above. The phthalide melts at 164°. (Found: Eq. wt., 282; C, 67.37; H, 4.49. $C_{16}H_{12}O_5$ requires Eq. wt., 284; C, 67.60; H, 4.23 per cent.).

(3'-Carboxy-4'-hydroxy-5'-methylbenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid, (VII).—It was obtained in the same way as the corresponding salicylic ester condensation product on using *o*-cresotinic acid methyl ester. Yield about 13 g. from 10 g. of phthalic anhydride. It crystallises in aggregates from acetic acid, m. p. 258-61° (decomp.). (Found: C, 63.80; H, 4.04. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 64.0; H, 4.0 per cent.).

Methyl-(3'-carbomethoxy-4'-hydroxy-5'-methylbenzoyl)-2-benzoate, (VIII).—It was obtained by esterifying the above in the usual manner, m. p. 103-04°. (Found: C, 65.61; H, 4.98. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 65.85; H, 4.88 per cent.).

(3'-Carboxy-4'-methoxy-5'-methylbenzoyl)-2-benzoic acid, (IX).—It was obtained by methylating (VII) in the usual manner. Crystals from acetic acid, m. p. 197-98°. (Found: C, 64.57; H, 4.51. $C_{17}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 64.96; H, 4.46 per cent.).

Methyl-(3'-carbomethoxy-4'-methoxy-5'-methylbenzoyl)-2-benzoate, (X).—It was obtained by esterifying (IX). Crystals from aqueous alcohol, m. p. 93°. (Found: C, 66.46; H, 5.41. $C_{19}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 66.66; H, 5.26 per cent.).

(3'-Carboxy-4'-hydroxy-5'-methylphenyl)-2-phthalide, (XI).—It was obtained by the reduction of (VII) as in the case of phthalylsalicylic acid. Flakes from aqueous alcohol, m. p. 204.05°. (Found: C, 67.29; H, 4.46. $C_{16}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 67.60; H, 4.23 per cent.).

(3'-Carboxy-4'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)-2-phthalide, (XII).—It was obtained by the reduction of (IX) with zinc dust and hydrochloric acid in presence of acetic acid. Aggregates from aqueous alcohol, m. p. 160°. (Found: C, 68.22; H, 4.71. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 68.46; H, 4.70 per cent.).

(3'-Carbomethoxy-4'-hydroxy-5'-methylphenyl)-2-phthalide, (XIII).—It was obtained by esterifying (XI) in the usual manner. Crystals from aqueous alcohol, m. p. 114-15°. (Found: C, 68.62; H, 4.89. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 68.46; H, 4.70 per cent.).